

A Stacked Analog-to-Digital Converter Providing 100 dB of Dynamic Range

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ABSTRACT

The dynamic range requirements of a modern radar system far exceed the dynamic range attainable with available ADC technology. Traditional ways of overcoming these dynamic range limitations, including STC, AGC, and IF limiting, have serious drawbacks. The Stacked ADC concept was developed to address the dynamic range limitations without the drawbacks of the traditional mitigation techniques. To demonstrate the concept, an experimental system based on the concept was built and tested. The resulting system demonstrated a dynamic range improvement over COTS ADCs of 30 dB, providing a total dynamic range of 100 dB.

1. INTRODUCTION

Increasingly, operation in littoral environments has become a necessity for the United States Navy. This environment, coupled with the advent of stealth technology for aircraft and missiles, has increased sensitivity and clutter suppression requirements for radar systems by several orders of magnitude. However, to meet these requirements, a dynamic range to the radar digital signal processor (DSP) is required that is much greater than that attainable with available analog-to-digital converter (ADC) technology. To increase the effective dynamic range to the radar DSP beyond the inherent ADC capability, a number of mitigation techniques have been used, including sensitivity time control (STC), automatic gain control (AGC), and bandpass intermediate frequency (IF) limiting. However, each of these mitigation techniques comes with serious drawbacks.

This paper describes a mitigation technique, referred to as a Stacked ADC, which overcomes many of the shortcomings associated with the aforementioned techniques. The Stacked ADC uses multiple ADCs, each connected to the same radar IF through amplifier chains with different gain factors. After digital amplitude and phase equalization, a composite dynamic range is realized that is much greater than the dynamic range of an individual ADC. Individual ADC limitations on signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and spurious responses will, however, not improve with this approach [1].

To demonstrate the feasibility and performance of this concept, a demonstration system based on the Stacked ADC concept was designed, built, and tested. A detailed description

of the demonstration Stacked ADC and of the results obtained during testing are presented in this paper.

2. RADAR DYNAMIC RANGE REQUIREMENTS

Among other requirements, a modern radar system should: provide maximum possible sensitivity, clutter suppression, and inter-clutter visibility at all ranges of interest; provide satisfactory handling of high-level electromagnetic interference (EMI); and provide accurate cross section measurements for targets and clutter. Maximum possible radar sensitivity, clutter suppression, and inter-clutter visibility at all ranges of interest is particularly important for the detection of stealth targets, where a significant detection margin may not be available, even at relatively short range. Clutter suppression and inter-clutter visibility become increasingly important in littoral environments, due to the natural terrain and man made structures. Satisfactory handling of high-level EMI also becomes increasingly important in littoral environments, due to the ease at which one could scatter jammers across the landscape. Accurate target and clutter cross-section measurements are often important for target recognition and discrimination, for suppression of false alarms caused by clutter residues, and for tracking accuracy,

Taken together, the requirements described above are a few of the requirements that drive the need for increased dynamic range to a radar digital signal processor. To simultaneously satisfy these requirements, a radar system must have the dynamic range to provide the sensitivity required for the detection of stealth targets while maintaining linear operation in the presence of much larger returns, since nonlinear operation results in degraded clutter attenuation due to intermodulation product generation [2], degraded inter-clutter visibility due to pulse compression sidelobe degradation, degraded visibility in jamming due to decreased sidelobe jamming cancellation and degraded tracking accuracy as well as other problems due to inaccurate cross-section measurements.

3. EXTENDING THE DSP DYNAMIC RANGE

In a high-power long-range radar system, clutter to noise ratios (CNR) can exceed 80 to 100 dB. The dynamic range required to linearly process such returns exceeds the dynamic

range capabilities of currently available ADCs by 20 to 40 dB. To address this discrepancy, a number of mitigation techniques have been used. AGC, STC, and bandpass IF limiting have traditionally been the most widely used mitigation techniques. These mitigation techniques, which constrain the dynamic range of an input signal to the dynamic range available from an ADC, permit a radar system to adequately satisfy some of the requirements listed in the previous section, however, this comes at the cost of inadequate performance with respect to other requirements.

Bandpass IF limiters allow one to maintain sensitivity in range-cells not affected by large clutter, however, they introduce substantial nonlinearities in the presence of large returns. On the other hand, RF AGCs can prevent receiver saturation due to large returns, but in doing so can introduce switching transients during gain adjustments which can lead to false alarms. To correct for this, one could fix the AGC setting for an entire CPI, however, this causes global desensitization and may necessitate an additional fill pulse to find the correct setting. Finally, STC may be the least desirable of these mitigation techniques. It can cause short-range detection degradation and pulse compression sidelobe degradation. Furthermore, STC is problematic with medium to high PRF radars, and, while STC is designed to prevent saturation due to short-range clutter, atmospheric effects such as ducting may effect propagation in such a way that long-range clutter will drive the dynamic range requirements.

4. THE STACKED ADC APPROACH

To address many of the limitations associated with the mitigation techniques discussed above, the Stacked ADC approach was developed at NRL. Figure 1 shows the basic concept of the Stacked ADC approach. A Stacked ADC replaces one ADC with N ADCs, each of which is connected to the radar receiver IF through a channel that differs in gain from the adjacent channel by Δ dB. The outputs of the ADCs are digitally equalized to bring all outputs into a common number system and to correct for channel-to-channel gain and phase discrepancies produced by hardware limitations. After equalization, the multiple channels of ADC data are combined, resulting in a data stream with a dynamic range $(N-1)\Delta$ dB greater than that of a single ADC data stream.

Figure 1: Basic Stacked ADC Concept

Channel combining with the Stacked ADC approach is based on a strategy that, on a range cell-to-range cell basis, selects equalized data from the most sensitive channel outputting uncorrupted data. With this strategy, equalization inaccuracies could cause degradation in clutter suppression if the channel used for a given range cell were to change during a CPI. If equalization inaccuracies were found to cause degraded clutter suppression, a strategy could be implemented that ensures the all data for a given range cell comes from the same ADC during a CPI, thereby ensuring optimal clutter suppression. This strategy could be realized by storing an entire CPI of ADC data and then, after the entire CPI had been stored, selecting for each range cell, the most sensitive ADC that was outputting uncorrupted data at that range cell for the entire CPI.

The Stacked ADC approach should provide the maximum possible sensitivity available under linear operation in each range-cell without introducing switching transients and without assumptions as to the PRF or clutter distribution. The chief limitation of the Stacked ADC approach is a SNR and SINAD in each range cell that cannot exceed that of a Single ADC. This limitation is due to the fact that for a given range-cell, data is only selected from a single ADC.

5. A STACKED ADC DEMONSTRATION SYSTEM

To demonstrate the feasibility and performance of the Stacked ADC approach, a demonstration system was built with the objective of providing 100 dB of dynamic range over a 20 MHz bandwidth. With the IF bandwidth selected, the IF frequency (f_{IF}) and ADC sampling frequency (f_s) for the system were chosen to avoid aliasing. A maximum theoretical IF bandwidth of $f_s/2$ can be accommodated if f_{IF} and f_s are related by the equation

$$f_s = \frac{4f_{IF}}{2M-1}, \quad (1)$$

where M is a positive integer. Therefore, to satisfy (1), the IF frequency and ADC sampling frequency of the system were chosen to be 60 MHz and 80 MHz respectively. The demonstration system used Analog Devices AD6645 ADCs (Table 1), which provide a dynamic range of approximately 73 dB. Using these ADCs, a dynamic range extension of approximately 30 dB was required to achieve a total dynamic range of approximately 100 dB. To realize this 30 dB extension, six channels with 6 dB gain differentials were used. These channels are referred to in this report as the 1x, 2x, 4x, 8x, 16x, and 32x channels, with the 1x being the least sensitive and the 32x being the most sensitive.

Channel equalization for the demonstration system was performed in real-time and consisted of multiplication of complex baseband data by complex equalization coefficients. The equalization coefficients were computed in real-time using received signals by the pair-wise division of baseband data from adjacent ADC channels. Tests conducted with the demonstration system to this point were done with CW signals and single pulses, so data combining was based on the strategy that took data from the most sensitive channel outputting uncorrupted samples. The digital signal processing tasks

performed by the Stacked ADC, including equalization and selection, are discussed in more detail in the DSP section that follows.

A major challenge in implementing the Stacked ADC approach was controlling signal power in the more sensitive channels while maintaining low noise. To do this in the demonstration system, receive signal strength indicators (RSSIs) were used in conjunction with solid-state switches. The RSSIs switched channels “off” when potentially damaging power levels were present. The Front End and RSSIs are also discussed in more detail in the following sections.

For the demonstration system, development cost and schedule were the driving factors in component selection. Following this selection philosophy, commercial off-the-shelf (COTS), connectorized analog components were used whenever possible, Analog Devices evaluation boards were used with the AD6645s, and a COTS FPGA board was used for digital signal processing. The only custom circuit boards that were designed were for the RSSIs, for the switches, and to interface with the DN3000k10S.

Front End

Figure 2 shows a block diagram of the front end for the Stacked ADC demonstration system. The specifications for the components are listed in Table 1. The front end was designed to accommodate 100 dB of dynamic range, from +12 dBm to -88 dBm, over a bandwidth of 20 MHz, and at an IF of 60 MHz. Also, the front end was designed to withstand input power levels up to 20 dBm.

Figure 2: Front End of Stacked ADC Demonstration System

Due to the 30 dB total gain differential required to create a Stacked ADC with 100 dB of dynamic range, a method was needed to restrict the power levels in all but the 1x channel to manageable levels when large receive signals were present. Previous versions of the Stacked ADC used limiting

operational amplifiers to perform this function, however due to excessive noise and harmonic generation as well as maximum input power restrictions, limiting operational amplifiers were not a feasible solution for this version of the Stacked ADC. Instead, as mentioned above, Hittite Microwave HMC221 solid-state switches were used in conjunction with Receive Signal Strength Indicators (RSSIs) to maintain manageable power levels. Large signals were detected by the RSSIs, which in turn threw the HMC221 switches into a 50Ω load, thereby reducing the signals to tolerable levels. With switches, the delays of the switching mechanism and the transients caused by switching had to be taken into account. To account for the 170 ns latency of the switching mechanism, extra coaxial cable was added in the path to the ADCs after the IF was coupled off to the RSSIs. To prevent switching transients from corrupting signals in other channels, buffer amplifiers and attenuators were placed immediately prior to the switches.

Table 1: Component Specifications

Mini-Circuits Hela-10D	Remec QB-101
Gain 11 dB	Gain 22 dB
Noise Figure 3.5 dB	Noise Figure 4 dB
IP2 88 dBm	IP2 105 dBm
IP3 49 dBm	IP3 54 dBm
P1dB 30 dBm	P1dB 31 dBm
Mini-Circuits ZFSC-2-1	Mini-Circuits ZFSC-3-1
Insertion Loss 0.3 dB	Insertion Loss 0.5 dB
Isolation 28 dB	Isolation 30 dB
Phase Unbalance 4 °	Phase Unbalance 3 °
Amp Unbalance 0.15 dB	Amp Unbalance 0.3 dB
Mini-Circuits SBP-60	Mini-Circuits ZFDC-20-4L
Insertion Loss 0.8 dB	Mainline Loss 0.2 dB
Center Frequency 60 MHz	Coupling 20.2 dB
3 dB BW 48.2-71.6 MHz	Coupling Flatness 0.5 dB
20 dB BW 44.9-76.6 MHz	Directivity 40 dB
Hittite HMC221	Analog Devices AD6645
Insertion Loss 0.4 dB	Resolution 14 Bits
Isolation 28 dB	Max Samp Rate 105 MHz
IP3 45 dBm	SNR 73.5 dB
P1dB 30 dBm	SINAD 73.0 dB
Switching Time 10 ns	SFDR 87.0 dB

Amplifiers were included after the switches so the desired gain could be achieved with tolerable power levels at the inputs to the switches. An additional amplifier was required in the 32x channel so the amount of attenuation between the buffer amplifier and the switch could be increased while maintaining the correct net gain. Before this additional amplifier was added, the HMC221 was being overdriven and taking several hundred microseconds to recover. COTS Mini-Circuits SBP-60 bandpass filters were included immediately before the ADCs to limit bandwidth and to reduce harmonic levels. Performance could have been improved with custom filters, however, the lead-time and cost of custom filters was prohibitive for this demonstration system.

Receive Signal Strength Indicators

As mentioned above, RSSIs were used to monitor the received signal strength and throw HMC221 switches into a

50Ω load when large signals were detected. An RSSI for each switch was connected to the output of the 20 dB coupler in the front end by way of a Mini-Circuits ZBSC-615 six-port power splitter (sixth port terminated). Each RSSI utilized an Analog Devices AD8310 demodulating logarithmic amplifier to gauge received signal strength. The AD8310 was configured to output a voltage, V_{OUT} , according to the equation

$$V_{OUT} = 0.1 \times (P_{IN} - 95) \text{ Volts} \quad (2)$$

where P_{IN} was the input signal power in dBm. A Maxim MAX961 comparator was used to compare V_{OUT} to a reference voltage and to throw the accompanying switch when the reference voltage was exceeded. The outputs of the comparators were buffered with CMOS buffers and sent to the switches and the DSP.

Digital Signal Processor

The digital signal processing configuration used in the demonstration system is shown in Figure 3. The inputs to the DSP were the samples from each ADC, the over range bit from each ADC, and the switch state bit from each RSSI. The samples and over range bits were synchronous inputs updated at an 80 MHz rate, while the switch state bits were asynchronous inputs. The outputs of the DSP were the equalized baseband samples with I and Q interleaved and the channel from which each equalized sample was selected. All of the outputs were updated at a 40 MHz rate.

Figure 3: Block Diagram of Digital Signal Processing

The equalization technique used for the demonstration system operated on complex baseband data. Therefore, incoming data was first fed to digital down converters (DDCs) to extract baseband data from the directly sampled IF data. The digital down converters digitally mixed the IF data to baseband, filtered the data with a 36-tap lowpass FIR filter, and decimated the result by a factor of 2 [3].

After digital down conversion, baseband data was selected on a range-cell-to-range-cell basis from the most sensitive, i.e. highest gain, channel outputting valid data. For a baseband sample, $s'[n]$, to be valid, each ADC sample, $s[n]$, used by the DDC FIR filters in the computation of the baseband sample must have been valid. The validity of each

ADC sample was determined by the state of the over range, or[n], and switch state, ss[n], bits. An ADC sample, was considered valid if the over range bit was inactive and the switch state bit was inactive and had been inactive for the preceding 11 samples. The latter condition allowed time for settling after switching.

Before outputting a complex sample, $s''[n]$, the selected data was equalized using the 32x channel as a reference channel. This equalization was performed through multiplication of the selected data by complex calibration coefficients. The calibration coefficients were computed using the recursive filter:

$$\alpha_{2^N x, 2^{N-1} x} = (1 - \beta) \frac{s'_{2^N x}[n]}{s'_{2^{N-1} x}[n]} + \beta \cdot \alpha_{2^N x, 2^{N-1} x} \quad N = 1 \dots 5 \quad (3)$$

with β selected to be 127/128. As is evident from Equation 3, each calibration coefficient equalized two adjacent channels. This strategy was used to maximize the SNR of the samples used for the calculation of the coefficients. With each coefficient equalizing two adjacent channels, one of the following multiplications was performed to equalize the selected data to the 32x channel:

$$s''[n] = s'_{1x}[n] \times \alpha_{2x,1x} \times \alpha_{4x,2x} \times \alpha_{8x,4x} \times \alpha_{16x,8x} \times \alpha_{32x,16x} \quad (4a)$$

$$s''[n] = s'_{2x}[n] \times \alpha_{4x,2x} \times \alpha_{8x,4x} \times \alpha_{16x,8x} \times \alpha_{32x,16x} \quad (4b)$$

$$s''[n] = s'_{4x}[n] \times \alpha_{8x,4x} \times \alpha_{16x,8x} \times \alpha_{32x,16x} \quad (4c)$$

$$s''[n] = s'_{8x}[n] \times \alpha_{16x,8x} \times \alpha_{32x,16x} \quad (4d)$$

$$s''[n] = s'_{16x}[n] \times \alpha_{32x,16x} \quad (4e)$$

$$s''[n] = s'_{32x}[n] \quad (4f)$$

During testing, equalization coefficients were computed continuously, but only forwarded to the equalizer at the start of a test.

All the digital processing for the demonstration system was done with a Dini-Group DN3000k10S COTS FPGA board. The DN3000k10S was populated with, among other components, a Xilinx Virtex II FPGA and three 36 X 1M ZBT SRAMS. The Virtex II performed the processing discussed above and the SRAM could have been used for CPI buffering if the selection strategy that bases selection decisions on a whole CPI of data was needed. Due to bandwidth limitations to the SRAM, the output complex data rate would have to be reduced to 20 MHz to implement CPI buffering. To interface with the DN3000k10S, a custom board was designed at NRL and manufactured by Capital Electro.

6. TEST RESULTS

To demonstrate the dynamic range of the Stacked ADC, a 60 MHz tone generated with an Agilent E8251A was input to the Stacked ADC and swept in power from -120 dBm to 20 dBm. Figure 4 shows the resulting input versus output measurement. To produce the output measurement, a DFT was performed on the data collected from the Stacked ADC and all bins of the DFT were summed in power. The output power was normalized to the power measured with no input to the Stacked ADC. These results demonstrate linear operation of the Stacked ADC over a 105 dB range, from -90 dBm to +15 dBm at the input.

Figure 4: Input vs. Output Characteristics of Stacked ADC

To demonstrate the potential benefits of the dynamic range extension realized with the Stacked ADC in more realistic scenarios, tests were also performed using simulated radar returns. These returns were captured with the Stacked ADC and with a stand-alone ADC to show the improved performance provided by the Stacked ADC over a single ADC. The waveform used for these tests, was a chirp with the nonlinear frequency versus time characteristic specified by the equation

$$f(x) = \frac{3.7x}{2} + \frac{3.0x}{2\sqrt{1-x^2}} \text{ MHz}, \quad (5)$$

where $x = \frac{2t}{\tau}$, and $-\frac{\tau}{2} < t < \frac{\tau}{2}$. The pulse width, τ , and rise

and fall-times for the chirp were 15 μs and 0.1 μs respectively. The chirp was compressed in MATLAB with a matched filter that had a phase response equal to the complex conjugate of the transmitted waveform phase response and an amplitude response that was Gaussian with a 6 MHz 3dB bandwidth.

To produce the simulated returns, data generated with a PC and MATLAB was uploaded to an Agilent 16522A pattern generator, which in turn fed an evaluation board containing an Analog Devices AD9857 Quadrature Digital Upconverter/Digital-to-Analog Converter (DAC). The analog output of the AD9857 evaluation board was amplified to provide sufficient power to drive the Stacked ADC to full-scale. However, the dynamic range available from the AD9857 was inadequate to exercise the full capabilities of the Stacked ADC, therefore, switches were included after amplification. The switches added an additional 59 dB of attenuation when small signals and/or low noise was required for testing of the system. The pattern generator used to feed data to the AD9857 also controlled these switches. The output of the switch combination connected to the input of the device under test (DUT). The output of the device under test was captured with an Agilent 16717A logic analyzer and transferred to a PC for pulse compression and analysis. A block diagram of the test setup that was used to perform these tests is displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Hardware for Generating Radar Returns

To compare the pulse compression performance of the Stacked ADC to that of a single ADC, a test was performed that utilized a return with only a single point target. For these tests, the magnitude of the return was set to -1 dBFS for the DUT. The data collected from the Stacked ADC and the single ADC, before and after pulse compression, is displayed along with the ideal data in Figure 6. The pulse compression sidelobe levels from the Stacked ADC were identical to those from the single ADC, and both levels were somewhat higher than those from the ideal data. It is believed that these discrepancies were due to limitations of the AD9857, because of the nearly identical performance from the Stacked ADC and the individual ADC. Important to note are the spurs present in the uncompressed data at the ranges of approximately 3 and 6.4 nmi. These spurs were produced by the switches used in conjunction with the AD9857. The noise present between the spurs demonstrates why the AD9857 could not be used without the ability to switch in greater attenuation; the noise level would have been too high to demonstrate the dynamic range of the Stacked ADC. The greater dynamic provided by the Stacked ADC compared to the single ADC is evident in Figure 21 by the lower noise level.

Figure 6: Simulated Return with Single Point Target

To provide a comparison of the Stacked ADC approach to the more conventional approaches using AGC or bandpass IF limiters, tests were performed with returns that had targets and clutter spread over a larger dynamic range. As shown in Figures 7 and 8, this return had point targets at 8.8 nmi, 14.5 nmi, and 22.4 nmi, that were respectively, when compressed, 126 dB, 71 dB, and 17 dB above the mean compressed Stacked ADC noise level. The target at 14.5 nmi was surrounded by clutter that was, on average, 100 dB above the

mean compressed Stacked ADC noise level. To mimic the behavior of an AGC, data was collected from a single ADC with the return strength set such that the largest returns were approximately -1 dBFS. To mimic the behavior of a bandpass IF limiter, returns from the Stacked ADC were digitally limited to the dynamic range of a single ADC. The return into the Stacked ADC was set such that the largest returns were approximately -1 dBFS.

Figure 7 depicts data captured from the Stacked ADC and from the ADC with an input at -1 dBFS. From the Stacked ADC data, all of the targets can be discerned. However, from the single ADC data, one can only discern the large target at 8.8 nmi and the target between clutter at 14.5 nmi. The target at 22.4 is not discernible due to noise.

Figure 7: Stacked ADC versus AGC Comparison

Figure 8 depicts data captured from the Stacked ADC and data mimicking IF bandpass limiting. Again, from the Stacked ADC data, all of the targets are discernable. However, from the data mimicking IF bandpass limiting, only the targets at 8.8 nmi and 22.4 nmi are discernible. The target at 14.5 nmi is masked by the degraded pulse compression sidelobes caused by limiting. Furthermore, though the target at 8.8 nmi is discernible, an incorrect cross section estimate would be produced for this target, also because of limiting.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Improved dynamic range is vital to improved radar performance, especially in littoral environments where strong clutter and propagation ducts are frequently present. Dynamic range requirements exceed the dynamic range attainable with available analog-to-digital converters by 20 to 30 dB. Furthermore, if the past is indicative of the future, it could be years or even decades before this gap is closed. Traditional techniques used to address this dynamic range shortfall, namely AGC, STC, and bandpass IF limiting, have many limitations that make them inadequate solutions to the problem. However, the Stacked ADC approach developed at NRL can provide the required dynamic range without many of the limitations associated with the traditional techniques.

Figure 8: Stacked ADC versus IF Limiting Comparison

The tests described for this paper demonstrate that the Stacked ADC approach is a promising way to meet the current and future dynamic range requirements with the COTS ADCs available today. The Stacked ADC demonstration system provided approximately 100 dB of dynamic range, extending the dynamic range of the COTS ADCs used by approximately 30 dB. This system provided the maximum available sensitivity in each range-cell without assumptions as to clutter distribution and while maintaining linear operation. The Stacked ADC performed as an ideal clairvoyant AGC with range-cell-to-range-cell switching. Switching transients were negligible in the system due to real-time calibration that was done with received signals. The accuracy of the calibration supported excellent pulse compression sidelobe performance. Clutter suppression was not demonstrated, but with a strategy that performed selection after buffering an entire CPI of data, one could ensure optimal clutter suppression while using the Stacked ADC approach. Though the system did introduce additional intermodulation distortion in the least sensitive channels, this is a minor problem that could be corrected with a slightly modified front end architecture.

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